

CONCEPT OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AND SOCIAL- ECOLOGICAL CULTURE

F.O.Mamajonova

Teacher of biology at the academic lyceum of
the Andijan state medical institute.

Abstract: This article provides a detailed analysis of the concept of sustainable development and its significance in solving modern global problems. It notes that problems such as depletion of natural resources, ecological crises, social inequality and economic inequality should be moderated on the basis of the principles of sustainable development. The article emphasizes the importance of socio-ecological culture and shows the need to achieve sustainable development through environmental ethics, conscious activity and rational management of resources. It is noted that the role of the education system, family education and the media in the formation of environmental responsibility is important. This work presents strategic approaches in the areas of harmonizing ecological and economic principles, saving natural resources, developing alternative energy sources and protecting the environment. The role of the media in raising environmental awareness is also analyzed separately.

Keywords: sustainable development, environmental sustainability, social sustainability, economic sustainability, socio-ecological culture, environmental ethics, environmental responsibility, education system.

INTRODUCTION

Sustainable development is one of the most important concepts in finding effective solutions to modern global problems. Currently, the rapid depletion of natural resources, environmental crises, social inequality and economic inequality are creating urgent problems for the world's population. In order to mitigate this

situation and meet the needs of future generations, it is important to apply the principles of sustainable development.

The concept of sustainable development was first presented in 1987 in the UN report “Our Common Future”, in which the term “sustainable development” was interpreted as meeting the needs of the present generation without compromising the ability of future generations to use resources. This concept includes three main areas: economic, environmental and social sustainability. Their integral integration is a decisive factor in ensuring the long-term development of society.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Socio-ecological culture is one of the most important factors of sustainable development. This culture represents a conscious process of activity aimed at maintaining the balance between humanity and nature, increasing ecological responsibility, and protecting the environment. Socio-ecological culture is a key component of sustainable development, which leads society to a sustainable state by raising environmental awareness and forming ecological ethics. The formation of this culture is considered an important tool in overcoming environmental and social crises in today's world.

The concept of sustainable development was first introduced in the UN report “Our Common Future” published in 1987. In this document, sustainable development is defined as: “Sustainable development is development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.”

A more precise expression of the concept of sustainable development was given at the UN Conference on Environment and Development held in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, in 1992. At this conference, “Sustainable development” was defined as a development model based on maintaining a balance between human activities and nature. As a result of the conference, the “Agenda 21” program was adopted, which set out the main directions of sustainable development.

Sustainable development includes three main components:

– environmental sustainability. This means protecting the environment and rational use of natural resources. Environmental sustainability is aimed at preserving them for future generations, taking into account the limited nature of natural resources.

–social sustainability. Ensuring social equality and justice, improving people's living conditions, and protecting their rights and freedoms constitute the social foundations of sustainable development.

– economic sustainability. Economic development should be carried out without wasting resources, while maintaining environmental and social sustainability. This includes supporting efficient production and innovation.

These three areas are interrelated, and the lack of any one of them limits the possibility of achieving overall sustainable development. For example, if economic development harms the environment, this undermines long-term stability. At the same time, social inequality leads to social conflicts and hinders overall development.

Socio-ecological culture refers to a culture aimed at maintaining the balance between human activity and nature. This concept includes the formation of environmental consciousness in society, the promotion of a responsible attitude of people towards nature.

Social culture here is manifested as the integration of environmental values with human social activities (education, art, science, production). For example, the formation of environmental consciousness and ethics, starting from preschool education, is important in ensuring that future generations live in accordance with the principles of sustainable development.

Ecological ethics expresses the moral responsibility of a person in protecting the environment. It includes the following basic principles in human activity: appreciation of nature as an integral part of human life, responsibility not to waste

resources and preserve them for future generations, and participation in environmental projects on a volunteer basis and demonstration of environmental activity.

The development of ecological responsibility requires changing the social consciousness of each individual in society. For this, the education system, family upbringing and the media are of great importance. Through a responsible approach, people become more aware of environmental problems and contribute to the preservation of nature.

The rational use of resources is one of the most important principles of sustainable development. Natural resources - water, air, forests and minerals - are limited, and their conservation and rational management are necessary to meet the needs of future generations. This principle is not only related to economic development, but also aims to ensure environmental sustainability.

Rational use means: Non-wastefulness and targeted use of resources, Development and expansion of alternative energy sources (solar, wind, hydropower), and Application of ecological innovations that replace non-renewable resources.

Saving and rational use of resources not only brings economic benefits, but also contributes to the sustainable development of society without harming the environment.

Respect for the environment is a fundamental ethical principle aimed at maintaining a balance between man and nature. Ensuring respect for the environment requires the following measures:

- a) protection and restoration of natural ecosystems;
- b) introduction of effective methods of pollution reduction and waste management;
- c) replacement of industrial and agricultural technologies that harm nature with environmentally friendly technologies.

Environmental responsibility should be implemented at the individual and collective levels. This means that each member of society must be responsible for the environment and take the necessary measures to protect nature. Socio-ecological culture plays a decisive role in the formation of ecological responsibility.

Education, family upbringing and social institutions have a special role in the formation of socio-ecological culture. In particular:

1. Education system:

– improving environmental literacy should be carried out starting from preschool education. Through education, students are given knowledge about nature protection and environmental responsibility;

–at higher levels, the principles of sustainable development are included in the curriculum, helping to form the ecological consciousness of the younger generation.

2. Family education:

– the family is the primary institution for the formation of ecological consciousness. Children learn to love and protect nature primarily in the family;

–the responsibility of parents in promoting environmental ethics is important.

3. Social institutions:

–legislation and government organizations should take decisive measures to protect the environment;

–non-governmental organizations contribute to sustainable development by implementing environmental projects and involving the public;

the media play a crucial role in highlighting environmental problems and raising awareness.

The following goals can be achieved through the media to develop environmental awareness in society:

–providing information about global environmental problems (climate change, resource scarcity) and local problems (soil salinization, water scarcity);

–informing the public about the consequences of environmental crises and

ways to eliminate them;

- the media can change public opinion through social advertising and special programs promoting environmental responsibility;

- involving the public in environmental projects and events. For example, disseminating information about tree planting campaigns, waste recycling campaigns.

By raising environmental awareness, the media serves as an important tool in forming a socio-ecological culture in society. This, in turn, creates a solid foundation for achieving sustainable development.

Sustainable development is of great importance as a basic principle in solving modern global problems. The interdependence of social, environmental and economic sustainability plays a crucial role in ensuring the long-term development of society. Through rational management of natural resources, the formation of environmental awareness and increased responsibility, it is possible to protect the environment, ensure social justice and achieve economic stability.

CONCLUSION

The education system, family education and the media are important tools for implementing the principles of sustainable development. Through these systems, it is possible to increase environmental responsibility in society, encourage conscious activity and educate the future generation in accordance with the principles of sustainable development.

In general, each person's responsible attitude towards the environment, environmental ethics and resource conservation activities serve as a key factor in achieving sustainable development. All three areas of sustainable development are interrelated, and if any of them is lacking, the possibility of achieving overall sustainability is limited. Therefore, implementing the principles of sustainable development based on an integrated approach is one of the most important tasks of the present era.

LIST OF REFERENCES

1. Pulatova N. Ijtimoiy ekologik ong va ekologik madaniyatning o‘zaro bog‘liqligi //Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №16.
2. 1987-yil BMTning Butunjahon atrof muhit va rivojlanish bo‘yicha Komissiyasi. Gro Xarlem Brundtland konsepsiyasi.
3. Шилова В.С. Социально-экологическая культура: сущность и особенности //Современные наукоемкие технологии. – 2009. – №. 3. – С.
4. Hediger W. Sustainable development and social welfare //Ecological economics. – 2000. – Т. 32. – №. 3. – С.
5. https://uz.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Barqaror_rivojlanish_maq_sadlari.